

Problem and Prospective Solution of “Persons with Physical Disabilities (P W D’s) Learners towards Higher Education

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Abstract

Education is the backbone of society and educational opportunity especially equal opportunities are the big issues in the education system. Right of children free and compulsory education RTE (Right to Education)-2009) already said for this concept, not only this but also Article- 23, Article- 21A, “National Policy of Education” (NPE)-1968 and 1986, also “New Education Policy-2020”, “District Primary Education Programme” (DPEP)-1985, “Persons with Physical Disabilities” (PwD) Act- 1995, “The Right of Persons with Disabilities” (RPwD)-2016 all have recommended for the inclusive education of the children who suffer from disabilities. Over time gap and recommendation of various policies and act it is still there being a gap in achieving education not only basic education but also higher education too. Higher educational institutions like college, university students mainly physically disable children facing lots of problems during his / her education. This paper focuses on that in the era of digital technology everything is possible with proper strategies. In the present study, the main objective is that 1. To study the problem in inclusive higher education faced by PwDs students. 2. To find out a suitable prospective solution. This study is based on secondary data; the Researcher collected the data from different journals, articles, eBooks, reports, and also reporting the result.

Keywords: RTE Act, The Right of Persons with Disabilities Act, Persons with Physical Disabilities, National Policy of Education, Digital Technology.

1. Introduction

Every person with a disability (PwDs) has a right to express their values and wishes concerning their education, with no compromise regarding education. 10% to 15% of the total world's population are belonging to be disabled. United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) was stated that, emerging global policy architecture for human rights for disabled people. India already introduced inclusive education for all levels but it's not implemented in proper ways. School education and higher education have different strategies for implementing the process. We are thinking in the viewpoint of higher education how to increase chances of employability in the various sectors thus, affirming dignified life for the persons with disabilities. If we think deeply and go through the various educational policies and programs related to Disabilities, we found a small number of works have been done in the field of higher education for disabled learners. A certain number of groups of people are working on the school education of children with disabilities. There are various reasons to not working in the field of higher education, like Infrastructural facilities within institutions, transportation facilities, lack of proper support services are available few areas and attitudes, perception towards persons with disabilities (PwDs) which is main hinder or gap for entry of new students with disabilities into any higher education. After post 2nd world war lots of changes in the field of various aspects and developed new ideologies and outlooks. On the other hand, after the feminist movement, racial discrimination movement, etc. movement was started regarding the disabilities movement has a recent history. During the early 1990s, Disability Acts not only started in the developed countries but also in the developing nations too. Disability issues have been important to protect human rights not only national level but also at the global level. Socio-economic, gender, racial, and political deprivation is the barrier for the society. Here only education, policies, and implementation are the main objects for the development PwDs section peoples. Recent education policy NEP-2020 also told about inclusive education in the same classroom situation but has not automatically transferred to our inclusion in higher education. The main stages of education like Elementary, secondary and higher education are two quite different entities in the process of admission, the framework of curriculum, governance policies, finance, and policy. That why it's the main issue in this paper disability becomes different in the higher education system in India.

2. Need and Significance of the Study

In Higher Education in India, inclusion is the most important term for analyzing and enhancement of equality and opportunities for disabled learners. In most developed societies' laws and acts regulations already more scientific on this section of people. Inclusive education literature, disabilities acts mention the various types of disabilities parameter and every different kind of disabilities learner are facing a different kind of problem during higher education in various sectors. Here try to understand the real problems of this learner and how to solve this particular problem in the real ground. We are observed in our colleges, universities, institutions lack of infrastructure of this section of learners and only a few numbers of students will continue his or her studies with lots of difficulties. Why not be more focused on this matter, only paperwork is not a suitable solution for a developing nation it must be implemented on the real ground level.

3. Objectives

- To study the Problem of “Persons with Physical Disabilities” section learners (PwD's) towards Inclusive Higher Education.
- To find out the prospective solution in accessing Higher Education for the Disabled learners.

4. Methodology of the Study

Secondary data-based paper, Researcher collected data from different sources there are e-books reports, policies, disability Acts, websites, observations of various organizations, journal articles, national and international articles published in local papers, etc. This paper will give a brief description of the Problem and prospective solutions of physical with disabilities section learners (PwD's) towards Inclusive Higher Education.

5. Meaning of Disability

There is a different kind of debate about the meaning and understanding of the disability concept. Historically, if a person's charity cases are normally called a disability, or from any purely medical perspective. But today, “Disability comes under within a human rights

framework. This shift in perspective and the marginalization of persons with a disability has pushed the issue of the rights of persons with a disability to the forefront of international debate”(International Paralympics Committee, 2004).

Disability is commonly misunderstood early, with that of handicap and impairment. “Disability is a condition caused by an accident, trauma, genetics or disease that may limit a person’s mobility, hearing, vision, speech or mental function” (Reynolds and Janzen 2007 p.735). Disability exists as it is situated in the larger context, while impairment is a biological condition (Braddock and Parish, 2001). Handicap is a physical and attitudinal constraint that is imposed upon a person regardless of whether the person has a disability. For example, some people with disabilities use wheelchairs. Stairs, narrow doorways, and curbs are handicaps imposed upon people with disabilities who use wheelchairs (Reynolds and Janzen, 2007 p.735).

Different Countries has different definition regarding of disability. According to the Persons with Disability Act (1995), In India Disability is mainly taken (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) where Disability means -mainly

- **Blindness**

- Blindness refers to a person who suffers following conditions, namely: -
- The total absence of sight or inability to see or a person with a low vision.
- Visual acuity or clearness not exceeding 6/60 or 20/200 (Snellen) is better with correcting lenses.
- Limitation of the field of observation subtending of 20-degree angle or worse.

- **Hearing Impairment**

- Hearing impairment means loss of hearing 60 (dB.) decibels or more then. He or she does not hear without the gadget.

➤ **Low Vision**

- A person with low vision means if a person's visual functioning is not working properly for daily lifestyle, him or her after treatment or standard remedial correction but who working help of using vision for the planning or execution of a task with an appropriate assistive device.

➤ **Locomotor disability**

- It means disabilities of bones, joints, or muscles, does not movement of the limbs.

➤ **Leprosy-Cured**

- “Leprosy cured person” means if any person is suffering from Loss of sensation in hands or feet, as well as senseless and paresis in the eye-lid problem but with no manifest deformity.

➤ **Mental retardation**

- Mental retardation means incomplete development of the mind of a person, major characterized by sub normality of intelligence.

➤ **Mental illness**

- Mental illness means any mental disorder other than a person with mental retardation.

The National Trust for The Welfare of Persons with Autism Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation, and Multiple Disabilities Act, 1999 Autism, and Cerebral Palsy are also included. “Autism” refers to the children having facing problems in his or their whole life for the different kinds of immeasurable disabilities condition those children are not grown and developed as a normal child, it is a kind of immature skill development with low communication and social abilities. The cause of autism may be environmental or genetic.

“Cerebral palsy” cerebral means ‘brain’ and palsy means ‘disorder is a kind of group of disorders when a specific area of the brain is damaged due to unconditional neurological function. Due to this disorder body movement and muscle condition is damaged.

Rights of PWD Act, 2016 (RPWD Act, 2016) “December 28, was passed this Act by both the houses. To empowerment, to inherent dignity, to freedom, and also own choice independent person”. This Act is a paradigm shift for the disabilities section.

5.1.Salient Features Of The Rights Of Persons With Disabilities Act, 2016

In the RPWD Act, 2016, “the list has been expanded from 7 to 21 conditions and it now also includes cerebral palsy, dwarfism, muscular dystrophy, acid attack victims, hard of hearing, speech and language disability, specific learning disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, chronic neurological disorders such as multiple sclerosis and Parkinson's disease, blood disorders such as hemophilia, thalassemia, and sickle cell anemia, and multiple disabilities”. The “mental retardation is replaced by intellectual disability”.at least 40% is

the “benchmark for Persons with disability under section 58(2) of the Act”. (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5419007/>)

5.2. Meaning of Inclusive Education:

Inclusive education means integrating the educational platform in the common learning environment for both students who have no special needs and the students who have special needs. It is an integration process in a common classroom environment.

According to UNESCO, inclusive education is seen as “a process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures, and communities, and reducing exclusion from education and from within education.”

Inclusive education is facilitated learning environments where teachers, learners welcome the diverse environment made a learning environment where every student has an opportunity to meet their needs and succeed.

Fig5.2: Model of Inclusive education.

5.3. Challenges of the students with disabilities in Higher education

- Physical inaccessibility: physical barriers in educational institutions like availabilities of the ramp, elevator in building block or the library, heavy doors, inaccessible washroom, etc.

- **Chataika (2010)** found based on interviews and observation “One of the big problems that we have here as students are that we need to study but the library has no access to books ...because the library has upstairs that we have to climb. These restrict people with disabilities to access some books. Some students fail to attend lectures because lecture rooms are located upstairs and some disabled students fail to climb to attend their lectures” (**Kabuta, L. 2014**). Also there is a problem in infrastructure from the secondary data it was found by taking interviews from the participants that infrastructure in higher education is not normally accessible for disabled learners.
- **Chataika (2010)** states that: - “For the disabled... the issue of the infrastructure limits enrolment of these students. Some qualified -very few qualified but like those people with physical disabilities look at the physical infrastructure and all along you say that they are not appropriate. So infrastructure development is also a limitation to accommodate some of these students”.

Lishner D, et, al. (1996) stated that “PWDs in rural settings confront a wide range of informational, geographical and financial barriers to health care access”.

Accommodation process: like scholarship, fellowship for the disabled students studying in higher education.

- Lack of individualization.
- Negative attitude and stereotype towards PwDs.
- Lack of available options.
- Lack of information to the families and prospective students about options.
- Insufficient equipment's, technological tools, and other devices for the teaching;

Mistry (2012) reported in his study that the students with disabilities did not have easy accessibility to classrooms, libraries, and academic and administrative buildings in their respective universities. They were also not provided with any kind of learning resources including assistive technology (**Ahmad, 2016**).

- Lack of proper training and support from the teachers:

Teacher educators are not trained properly for the inclusive classroom through the teacher educators are trained to handle the disabled students theoretically but still, there is a gap in practical training to cope up with the disabled students.

- Large classroom size and lack of environment: due to the large classroom size the teacher can't keep more attention to the disabled students as per their needs. Also, some classroom environments not so joyful for disabling learners.
- Lack of government support and facilities in Higher education for the Disabilities:

Government initiative also more important at the stage of Higher education, though the government commencement took place the frequency of it rather poor.

Hasanuzzaman and Khan (2011) reported higher bureaucratized system with multiple controls and regulations by Central and State Government and statutory bodies, outdated programs with inflexible structure, inadequate infrastructural facilities, lack of trained manpower, funds, training facilities, techniques, and research for the disabled and high unit cost of higher education, particularly of professional education are the causes for the limited accessibility of higher education for individuals with disabilities.(**Ahmad, 2016**).

6. Prospective Solution for Accessing Higher Education for the Disable learners:

Levesque J, et.al. (1996) stated that “Equitable access to everyone requires primary health care is important and it’s also globally emphasis for disabling learners”.

Lishner D, et, al. (1996) stated that “However, in the rural area persons with disabilities (PWDs) generally facing more barrier due to more general”.

Terrain and climate

Vergunst R, et.al (2015)“Given the long-distance and limited transportation, papers also recounted the experiences of participants in navigating geographical features as they try to seek care. In particular, persons using wheelchairs in rural South Africa had to navigate mud and gravel”.

Van Hees S, et.al (2015) “stated that was exacerbated during the rainy season when people had to use their wheelchairs in wet conditions in hilly areas”.

If climate and terrain condition is favourable then it will be help full for easily accessible for PWDs.

The equitable access needs to affordable health care is very essential for the development of PWDs children.

Perceived quality of care

Goodridge D, Rogers M, Klassen L, Jeffery B, Knox K, Rohatinsky N, et al. (2015) stated that “Clients’ perceptions about the care was discussed in some papers. For persons with mental disorders, their decisions to seek care were largely influenced by those with previous experiences at health facilities”.

- ✓ Needs to change infrastructure change and modification in every university to free access for the disabled learners. Like constructing a ramp, side by side on the stair, use of the elevator in each section of the building blocks
- ✓ Giving the accommodation and available option to enter higher education
- ✓ Reforming the policy statements and framework of the implementation
- ✓ Reforming the teacher education curriculum to create an inclusive teacher
- ✓ Increase college and University in nearest district or as well as states
- ✓ The inclusive environment in a classroom and also in college or university

7. Conclusion:

There are so many policies that are reflecting about the problems of disabled learners though there is a lack of recommendation on higher education. India as well as the whole world are also working on education for the disabilities section of the people. Many universities and colleges also develop their infrastructure for this section of learners. We are discussed here in the use of various ways to find out problems and expected solutions in higher education to achieve a different kind of policies objectives. Disability is not a problem of a particular section of the people it's a problem of a different kind of awareness mindset. We have to move towards an Inclusive society by making the chance and equal opportunities for disabled learners in education. Written work is not only a solution for it but also the focus should be on the grass-root level, so we have to make practical opportunities for the disabled learners in education not only at primary and secondary level but also higher education too. In the present situation disabled learners can reach to meet their higher secondary education but very few learners have got opportunities to join in higher education or universities.

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